

ISic1063

I.Sicily inscription 1063

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone (local)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Mutyca

Place of origin (modern)

Modica

Provenance

Molino della Lardereria, grotta della signora

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Ragusa, Museo Archeologico
Ibleo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140543

1. ²See IG XIV 245.²

2.

Edition: PHI140545

1. Ἀντώνιος Σα-

2. τρονίλος ἐνθά-

3. δε κίτε· ἐκοι-

4. μήθη μηνὶ Δεκ (εμ) β (ρίω)

5. ἀπὸ καλ (ανδῶν) ζ'.

6. Ἀντωνεῖα

7. Εὐτυχεία

8. ἐνθάδε κίτ [ε]

9. [ἐκ]οιμήθη

10. [— — — —]

11.

Edition: PHI140547

1. ²See IG XIV 245.²

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492694

EDCS 39102220

PHI 140543

PHI 140545

PHI 140547

Bibliography

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